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CURRENT STATE AND PROSPECTS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF MOTOR BIOFUELS IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to elaborate a scenario for the development of Ukraine's motor biofuels market. In recent years, the production and consumption of bioethanol in Ukraine have been relatively low despite the operation of several bioethanol plants. The production and consumption of biodiesel fuel have been practically absent, and the use of biogas/biomethane in transport sector has not been implemented yet in the country. The suggested scenario is based on the improved assessment of biomass potential for 2021 and 2050 as well as on the basic approach and assumptions used in the Roadmap for Bioenergy Development in Ukraine until 2050 elaborated by the Bioenergy Association of Ukraine. The developed scenario is basic and generally in line with Ukraine's draft National Renewable Energy Action Plan until 2030. The envisaged production volume of biofuels in 2050 practically corresponds to the full forecasted potential of relevant biomass types in Ukraine for that period. The implementation of this scenario involves overcoming at least some of the main barriers existing in Ukraine's motor biofuels sector. To launch the process, it is necessary to establish a mandatory share of bioethanol in gasoline and biodiesel in diesel fuel.

Keywords: biofuels, motor biofuels, biofuels market, bioethanol, biodiesel.

Introduction.

Decarbonisation of energy, including the transport sector, is one of the current global challenges. The consumption of biofuels can reduce greenhouse gas and exhaust emissions as well as decrease dependence on fossil fuels. The development of production and consumption of motor biofuels is of vital importance for Ukraine as the country is entirely dependent on the imported oil products, which make up the biggest share of Ukraine's imports (about 20% in 2021).

The consumption of liquid motor fuels in Ukraine during 2017-2021 was quite stable with some small fluctuations: gasoline 1.7-2.0 mln t/y, diesel fuel 5.1-5.8 mln t/y. The total consumption of natural gas in the country during this period had a slight tendency to decrease, at that gas consumption in transport was reduced by more than twice, from 2.3 bln m³ in 2017 to 1.0 bln m³ in 2020.

In recent years, the production and consumption of bioethanol in Ukraine have been relatively low. In particular, about 140 kt of the biofuel were consumed in 2019 and 81 kt in 2020. In addition, the exports of bioethanol to the EU amounted to 6.5 kt in 2020 and 28 kt in 2021. There are 22 small bioethanol plants in Ukraine, which in total can produce about 400 kt/y of the biofuel. Of them, 7 plants are new private factories, the rest is reconstructed old state factories. Currently, only a few bioethanol plants are operating stably at full capacity, the rest is actually idle. Besides, 14 large biodiesel plants of 300 kt/y total production capacity were built in Ukraine in the 2000s. However these plants have been actually idle, mostly due to economic factors, so now biodiesel is not practically produced in the country. The blockade of Ukrainian ports and problems

connected with the export of agricultural products made agrarians consider the possibility of processing these products within the country. One of the promising options is the domestic production of motor biofuels.

Despite the current weak development of motor biofuels sector in the country, the draft National Renewable Energy Action Plan until 2030 sets quite ambitious goals for further development of this sector. By 2030, it is planned to increase the consumption of bioethanol up to 238 ktoe/y (including 48 ktoe/y of the advanced biofuel) and the consumption of biodiesel up to 87 ktoe/y (including 17 ktoe/y of the advanced biofuel). It is important that despite some problems and barriers, Ukraine has quite good preconditions to achieve these goals, one of main prerequisites being large potential of feedstock (Geletukha 2022).

Methodology.

When developing a scenario for the production of motor biofuels in Ukraine, the existing global and European trends in this and related areas were taken into account, including main provisions of Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (RED II) and the European Green Deal. Ukraine as a potential EU member will most probably join the implementation of the European Green Deal. It is possible that Ukraine will be allowed a certain leeway in time for the fulfilment of its goals, for example, 10 years. Therefore, Ukraine should be now actively engaged in activity on transport decarbonization as an important component of the European Green Deal (Zheliezna 2021).

Analysis of the forecast balance of motor biofuel market in the EU until 2032 shows the following main trends (EC 2022):

- Practically no increase in the production of I-generation biodiesel and bioethanol.

- Some increase in the production of advanced biofuels, the average annual rise during 2022-2032 being 15.6% for bioethanol and 11.3% for biodiesel.

- Decrease in bioethanol and biodiesel exports into the EU, the average annual reduction during 2022-2032 being 3.3% for bioethanol and 2.4% for biodiesel.

According to the existing forecasts (OECD-FAO 2022), the total consumption of bioethanol in the world will increase by 10 bln l/y up to 140 bln l/y in the period of 2022-2031. The growth of consumption is expected at the expense of Brazil, India and some other countries. The global use of biodiesel until 2031 will remain unchanged at the level of about 55 bln l/y. At that, the consumption of biodiesel will decrease in the EU and the USA, while it will slightly rise in Brazil, Indonesia, Argentina, and Thailand. It is expected that the largest importers of bioethanol in 2031 will be Brazil, the USA, Japan, Canada and the United Kingdom, and importers of biodiesel will be the EU, the USA, the United Kingdom, Canada, and Peru.

The suggested scenario for the development of motor biofuels market in Ukraine is founded on the improved assessment of biomass potential for 2021 and 2050 as well as on basic approach and assumptions used in the Roadmap for Bioenergy Development in Ukraine until 2050 elaborated by the Bioenergy Association of Ukraine (Geletukha 2021).

Main part.

Ukraine has a considerable potential of biomass available for the production of various types of biomass

fuels and energy. According to 2021 data, this potential is about 26 Mtoe/y, of which solid biomass accounts for 62%, biogas for 31% and biofuels for 7%. The assessment of biofuels production potential includes biodiesel from rapeseed (70% of the crop harvest is taken in the calculation) and biodiesel from oilseed energy crops (cultivation on 0.5 mln ha is assumed), as well as bioethanol from corn grain (10% of the crop harvest is taken in the calculation).

In 2021, more than 90% of rapeseed was exported from Ukraine, mainly to European countries. In the European Union, almost 70% of rapeseed (produced and imported) is used for the production of biodiesel (Krautgartner 2022, Flach 2022). Focusing on the development of domestic production of biodiesel (and not on the export of rapeseed to obtain biodiesel abroad), we believe that 70% of the rapeseed harvest can be used for the production of biodiesel in Ukraine.

The analysis and comparison of data on corn production and processing in the world (USDA 2023), as well as the production of bioethanol from various types of raw materials (OECD-FAO 2022), show that about 13% of corn harvest was processed into bioethanol in the world in 2021. Based on this, we consider it expedient for Ukraine to assume that 10% of the produced corn grain can be processed into bioethanol.

According to the adopted approach, the possible production of biodiesel from rapeseed and oilseed energy crops is estimated at 0.88 Mtoe/y, and bioethanol from corn is estimated at 0.86 Mtoe/y (Table 1).

Table 1.

Assessment of the current and prospective potential of feedstock for the production of biofuels in Ukraine.

Type of biofuel and feedstock	Theoretical production potential, mln l/y	Potential available for energy (the economic potential)	
		Share of the theoretical potential, %	Mtoe/y
2021			
<i>Biodiesel:</i>	1412	78	0.88
- from rapeseed (70% of the total seed harvest)	1052	70	0.58
- advanced biodiesel from oilseed energy crops cultivated on unused agricultural land (0.5 mill ha)*	360	100	0.29
<i>Bioethanol</i> from corn (10% of the total grain production)	16844	10	0.86
TOTAL	18256	15	1.73
2050			
<i>Biodiesel:</i>	1889	82	1.24
- from rapeseed (70% of the total seed harvest)	1052	70	0.58
- advanced biodiesel from used cooking oil (UCO)*	117	75	0.07
- advanced biodiesel from oilseed energy crops cultivated on unused agricultural land (1 mill ha)*	720	100	0.59
<i>Bioethanol:</i>	35875	7	1.29
- from corn (5% of the total grain production)	21055	5	0.54
- advanced bioethanol from corn stover (10% of the total amount of residues)	14820	10	0.76
TOTAL	37764	11	2.53

* In the assessment, biodiesel of this type is considered advanced since according to RED II, it is not subject to restrictions on biofuels produced from food/feed crops.

Expert assessments show the possibility of a considerable increase in the bioenergy potential of Ukraine until 2050 (Geletukha 2021). The main factors of the growth include increase in the yield of crops (primarily cereals); expansion of area under energy crops and rise of their yield; use of 20% of arable land for growing cover crops for biogas production; involvement of new feedstock types for the production of motor biofuels and some other factors. Considering these points, Ukraine's bioenergy potential in 2050 p. is estimated at about 44 Mtoe/y, which is 1.7 more than the potential in 2021. At that, the production potential for biodiesel is projected to be 1.24 Mtoe/y and for bioethanol – 1.29 Mtoe/y in 2050 (see Table 1).

When forecasting the production potential for biofuels in 2050, the production of advanced bioethanol from lignocellulosic feedstock was taken into account (Tran 2020), as well as the involvement of new types of raw materials, for example, used cooking oil (Suzihaque 2022) to obtain advanced biodiesel. It should be noted that the potential of feedstock for I-generation

bioethanol in 2050 is limited to 5% of the corn grain harvest, so the possible volume of production is lower than in the estimate for 2021. However, due to the growth of corn yield considered in the calculation, this decrease is only 37%, and not 50%. The reduced potential volume of I-generation bioethanol production in Ukraine takes into account the existing pan-European trend to limit the production of biofuels from food/feed crops and to stimulate the production of advanced motor biofuels.

Taking into account the above-mentioned factors and trends, as well as the features of Ukraine's conditions, a scenario for the production of motor biofuels in the country is proposed as shown in Figure 1. According to this scenario, the total annual production of biofuels in 2050 may reach 2530 ktce, including bioethanol from corn grain – 535 ktce, advanced bioethanol from corn stover – 755 ktce, biodiesel from rapeseed – 580 ktce, advanced biodiesel from used cooking oil and oilseed crops cultivated on unused agricultural land – 660 ktce.

Figure 1. Suggested scenario for the production of motor biofuels in Ukraine until 2050.

The elaborated scenario is a basic one which is generally in line with the mentioned earlier draft National Renewable Energy Action Plan until 2030. The envisaged production volume of biofuels in 2050 practically corresponds to the full forecasted potential of relevant biomass types in Ukraine for that period. The implementation of this scenario involves overcoming at least some main barriers existing in Ukraine's motor biofuels sector. If all the barriers are quickly overcome and sufficient funding is available, the dynamics of achieving the 2050 indicators may be more positive.

This means that the production volumes of motor biofuels in 2030 and subsequent years will be higher than those in the presented basic scenario.

Based on data on the use of gasoline and diesel fuel in Ukraine in 2021 (2.0 Mt and 5.7 Mt, respectively), the volume of the domestic market for bioethanol can be estimated as 210 kt/y (on condition of blending 10% of the biofuel with gasoline), and that for biodiesel is 290 kt/y (on condition of blending 5% of the biofuel with diesel fuel). In the case of production of hydrotreated vegetable oil (HVO), the amount of its use in Ukraine's domestic market can be much larger, since

the properties of HVO allow its use as a direct substitute for diesel fuel. When Ukraine has a large number of flex-fuel vehicles, the volume of bioethanol consumption in the domestic market can also be considerably higher. The volume of produced biofuels that exceeds the domestic demand can be exported.

We believe that in the period until 2050, the possibility of exporting motor biofuels will remain, primarily advanced ones (which are sustainable). According to the forecast on global energy perspective until 2050 (McKinsey 2022), the global demand for sustainable motor fuels will grow until 2035 (up to ~ 220 mln t/y) with a subsequent decrease to the level of 2025 (~ 170

mln t/y). By 2050, the largest growth in demand is expected for sustainable fuel from lignocellulosic feedstock; in addition, there will remain quite a large demand for fuel from oil of agricultural crops.

Under present conditions, the production of I-generation bioethanol (from grain and molasses) and biodiesel from used cooking oil is feasible in Ukraine with the simple payback period < 5 years (Table 2). To achieve feasible production of biofuels from other feedstock types, it is necessary to perfect respective technologies and production processes, look for cheaper feedstocks, improve general logistics and management of the production processes or even seek for state support or some preferences.

Table 2.

Results of feasibility study of biofuels production.

Indexes	Bioethanol from corn grain	Bioethanol from straw	Biodiesel from rape-seed oil	Biodiesel from UCO
Biofuels productivity, kt/y	50	50	50	20
Operational time, h/y	8000			
Feedstock consumption, kt/y	152	250	50.7	22.2
Purchase price of feedstock, EUR/t without VAT	155	35	856	300
CAPEX, mln EUR	32	140	55.5	26.7
OPEX, mln EUR/y	35.0	61.64	53.4	11.3
Biofuels production expenses, EUR/l	0.553	0.974	0.945	0.500
Depreciation charges, EUR/l	0.020	0.088	0.039	0.047
DDG* sale price, EUR/t without VAT	112.5	–	–	–
Income from DDG sale, mln EUR/y	5.1	–	–	–
Corn oil* sale price, EUR/t without VAT	1145.8	–	–	–
Income from corn oil sale, mln EUR/y	2.2	–	–	–
Electricity* sale price, EUR/kWh without VAT	–	0.15	–	–
Income from electricity sale, mln EUR/y	–	6.6	–	–
Sale price of crude glycerine*, EUR/t without VAT	–	–	100	100
Income from sale of crude glycerine, mln EUR/y	–	–	0.51	0.20
Production cost of biofuels, EUR/l	0.46	0.96	0.98	0.54
Approximate sale price of biofuels**, EUR/l without VAT	0.65	1.2	1.1	1.1
<i>Economic assessment of the projects</i>				
Loan share of CAPEX, %	70			
Lending period, years	5			
Loan rate in EUR, %	6			
Internal return rate (IRR), %	32.9%	9.8%	12.7%	41.1%
Simple payback period, years	4.1	10.6	8.6	3.5

* DDG (distiller's dried grains), corn oil, electricity and crude glycerine are byproducts of different technologies of bioethanol production.

** The price does not take into account the excise tax of 100 EUR/1000 l.

Findings.

Being highly dependent on the imported oil products, Ukraine urgently needs to develop domestic production of bioethanol and biodiesel. It is necessary for several reasons: to decrease the consumption of conventional gasoline and diesel, to cut expenses on the imported oil products, to achieve the planned national targets on biofuels in the transport sector, and to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from transport.

Ukraine has quite good prerequisites, including the large feedstock base, for the development of domestic biofuel market. To launch the process, it is necessary to remove a number of existing barriers, first of all, to

establish a mandatory share of bioethanol in gasoline and biodiesel in diesel. The suggested binding share for bioethanol is 10% for the existing (not modified) gasoline engines and up to 50-85% for flexible fuel vehicles in the future, when such vehicles are widely used in the country. For biodiesel, the suggested mandatory share is 5% of the biofuel in diesel fuel.

Recently, several draft laws aimed to introduce an obligatory share of biofuels have been developed in Ukraine. Some of these draft laws have been even adopted in the first reading, however the process has not been completed. We consider it necessary to update and put the finishing touches on one of them and passed

it in the near future. That would be a considerable push for the development of motor biofuels sector in Ukraine.

References:

1. EC 2022. EU agricultural outlook for markets, income and environment, 2022-2032. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis/markets/outlook/medium-term_en
2. Flach B., Lieberz S., Bolla S. 2022. Biofuels Annual. USDA Report E42022-0048.
3. Geletukha G.G., Zheliezna T.A. 2021. Prospects for bioenergy development in Ukraine: Roadmap until 2050. *Ecological Engineering & Environmental Technology*, 22(5), 73–81. <https://doi.org/10.12912/27197050/139346>
4. Geletukha G.G., Zheliezna T.A., Matveev Yu.B. et al. 2022. Energy production from biomass in Ukraine: technologies, developments, perspectives. *Akadempriodyka*, Kyiv. <https://doi.org/10.15407/akademperiodyka.464.373>
5. Krautgartner R., Omnes M.A., Rehder L. et al 2022. Oilseeds and Products Annual. USDA Report E42022-0031.
6. McKinsey 2022. Global Energy Perspective Report. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/oil-and-gas/our-insights/global-energy-perspective-2022>
7. OECD-FAO 2022. Agricultural Outlook 2022-2031. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/f1b0b29c-en>
8. Suzihaque M.U.H., Alwi H., Ibrahim U.K. et al. 2022. Biodiesel production from waste cooking oil: A brief review. *Proceedings of 2nd International Conference on Chemical Engineering and Applied Sciences (Supplement)*, pp. S490-S495. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.04.527>
9. Tran T.T.A. et al. 2020. Bioethanol Production from Lignocellulosic Biomass. *Alcohol Fuels - Current Technologies and Future Prospect*. IntechOpen. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.86437.
10. USDA 2023. World Agricultural Supply and Demand Estimates. Report WASDE - 632.
11. Zheliezna T.A. 2021. European Green Deal and new opportunities for renewable energy development. *Thermophysics and Thermal Power Engineering*, 43(1), 75-81. <https://doi.org/10.31472/ttpe.1.2021.9>